

DIDACTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF COMMUNICATIVE TRAINING IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract. *Communicative training is widely used in the educational process today. Communicative training is an educational process aimed at understanding, activating, forming and improving personal qualities necessary for interaction with students and teachers. This is training in the ability to build a communication process taking into account the situation, interests and goals of students, colleagues, and the team.*

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There are many ways and styles of learning languages. One of them is communicative training. In the popularity rating, this teaching method has long and reliably taken the first place among all other methods.

Communicative knowledge and communicative education as a type of social experience includes many methods and approaches that reflect the uniqueness of the social contexts and educational traditions of a certain country, culture and its social institutions. At the same time, despite the variety of approaches and their own characteristics, the method of determining the meaning of our world and sharing this meaning with others (which actually constitutes the essence of communication), on the one hand, is ancient art, on the other hand - modern scientific knowledge. This scientific knowledge, of course, is included in the content of communication education, and modern education determines this content.

In Russia, French and other living languages are taught in modern methods based on the principles of so-called communicative education. This is primarily due to the fact that the audience is a strong motivating factor here. Today, the worldly, social and political life of competitive personnel requires knowledge of foreign languages. Since there is a real demand in society, foreign language teaching is actively developing. At the same time, the student's family actively participates in the training and creates the necessary language environment, where he is forced to speak a foreign language. Thus, the training here goes from oral speech to the language and writing system.

This method of teaching fully reflects the principles of modern communicative methods focused on "living" language and its use in situations. This method involves the immersion of the learner in the language environment, the use of the mother tongue is minimized or completely eliminated. However, this method entered educational institutions more than a century later. He spread the grammar-translation method to the study of living languages in general education schools. Until the 1990s, there were no generalized studies describing the traditions of communicative education in Russia and other countries. It was at this time that English began to become an international language. At that time, there were such techniques as grammatical

translation method, audiolingual, and others. All of them have shortcomings and people who learn English as a foreign language find that they do not meet their needs.

People who learned English to communicate in it did not know spoken language and knew nothing about oral etiquette. That is, they were upset during real communication. This method uses many techniques previously used in other methods. This method is different from others, because the educational fiction texts, which are far from life, are replaced by dialogues from everyday life. Students play with them in such a way that they invite each other to a conversation, that is, they stimulate the other person.

«Hello, my name is Maria. I live in London. I am a student»

«Salom, mening ismim Mariya. Men Londonda yashayman. Men o'quvchiman» it is replaced by the study of "Dating", where they actually get to know each other, ask each other various questions, discuss something. The first step is to discuss topics that students are familiar with in their own language. In this way, it develops students' ability to use the language independently. Topics should be relevant and interesting for students.

The difference between communication and other existing methods is that students who engage in this method do not know how the lesson will end, who will answer this or that question, and how, it all depends on the situation. Each lesson has new topics for discussion, new types of exercises. This is done so that the students are diverse and, at the same time, do not get tired of learning.

Communicative training is necessary, first of all, to overcome the fear of live communication. A reader who is not afraid of misunderstandings, has mastered standard grammatical structures and has a vocabulary of up to 1000 words, can easily find a common language abroad. But every medal has a flip side. In this case, it was poor lexicon and clichéd expressions. And if you add grammatical errors to that, you can easily earn a reputation for not being very conversational.

Advantages There is an opinion that teaching English using communicative training is best for those who have some lexical and grammatical bases of the language acquired in school, university or basic courses. In addition, the advantages:

Students speak English from the first lesson. Communicative training technology of teaching English assumes that students are immersed in an English-speaking environment from the first lesson. If you have not even thought about how to speak English, then after the first lesson you will be able to learn several dozen phrases and use them in conversation.

Language barrier: Without hesitation, competent speech is the main goal of communication training. A language barrier occurs when a learner is afraid of making a mistake in pronunciation or cannot get rid of an accent. Communicative training technique perfectly overcomes all this, because the practice of communication is allocated to almost all the specified times. At the same time, the teacher corrects your mistakes and encourages students who are not afraid to express themselves in English.

Fluency: In class, students only talk about things they encounter every day: daily problems, talking with friends, discussing the news, etc. Therefore, the use of communication training will develop communication skills in English as well as in your native language.

Good language comprehension: In the classroom, students not only talk, but also listen to other students. Students need to understand what the interlocutor is talking about in order to have a full dialogue. In this way, students' listening skills develop well. Later, students can

independently watch original movies, listen to music and understand without problems, as well as talk freely with foreigners.

Rapid expansion of vocabulary: Communicative training technology in English classes is designed for those who want to learn English quickly and interact with students. Therefore, in the first month of study, students will learn about 50-70% of the words that English people use every day, and the students' vocabulary will reach 3000-4000 words, which is travel, business trip, communication and even enough to read the news.

Almost Everywhere: Communicative training technology is so popular that almost all language learners can use it. In addition, through communicative training, students do not need expensive textbooks or additional grammar lessons, only lively communication and a pleasant mood.

Interesting and simple lessons: The lessons do not use topics that will bore the students. Students are engaged in interesting activities: they play educational games, communicate and help each other.

In addition, students are given relatively little homework. Therefore, absolutely everyone can learn English in this way.

Disadvantages: Like any method of learning a foreign language, communicative training technology has its disadvantages. The main problem is that it is very difficult for a beginner to learn the complex grammar basics presented immediately in a foreign language. In addition, the following disadvantages can be distinguished:

The complete abandonment of the native language, which is mandatory for teaching methods through communicative training technology, can be stressful for uneducated students. Compulsory work excludes the opportunity to work one-on-one with the teacher in pairs and groups. A teacher who uses the communicative teaching method during the lesson cannot devote enough attention and time to each pair of groups.

Who is the communication training technology for teaching English and for whom it will be useful to learn it? Let's see what goals can be achieved by learning English with the help of this technology:

First of all, these are those who want to speak very competently, because it is this skill that comes first, and this technology works to improve it. Students learn not only to speak on various topics, but also to actively monitor the correctness of their speech. The above-mentioned speech impediment often arises from a person's fear of making mistakes in speech. Learning technology is very active in combating this fear. About 70% of each class time is spent on the development of speaking skills. Lessons allow you to remove the psychological barrier, because students completely lose the fear of speaking English.

Secondly, for those who want to speak fluently, teaching technology will definitely be useful. The principle of the lessons is that the students speak English more and more often, so they learn to form their thoughts much faster than in regular lessons. This is because the teacher talks to the students in such a way that it is very easy and interesting to answer any question. In addition, the knowledge gained is used to the maximum every time. Students are able to speak more coherently, often using so-called clichés. Thus, it becomes possible to speak fluently, just remember the correct inflection and make the correct chain of phrases.

Thirdly, the communicative method is intended for those who want to not only hear, but also understand the English language. During the conversation with the teacher, you will be given

the opportunity to listen to the consistency of natural English speech. Students get used to this speech very quickly, and the ear understands words well, including those that are not yet familiar. In class, students listen to material and analyze interesting audio and video materials with the teacher. Each material is often used as a basis for discussion.

Fourth, for those who want to stop translating their thoughts from Russian to English, it is necessary to pronounce a certain phrase every time. This technology is aimed at developing the ability to speak and think independently on various topics. Even beginners will learn a dozen or two important phrases that they can actively use in everyday life after the first lesson. Those who have started to attend the courses and have knowledge of only the first three stages are initially given explanations in Russian, but this takes up to 5-10% of the lesson. And if necessary, beginners can use the Russian language themselves, but soon they will begin to form their thoughts without additional translation. The mental construction of a word in English greatly facilitates and speeds up the process of forming it.

Fifth, the communicative approach is perfect for those who want to learn grammar and new words for direct conversation. The classes are aimed at eliminating the fear of learning grammatical inflections, because the very simple principle of learning all structures is implied here - no one is trying to cram theory and learn it by heart. The same principle works with new words. Everywhere, only their repeated practical use is observed. An interesting topic is being discussed, in this process new construction or vocabulary is used in practice, that is, in the process of conversation. Five to ten sentences on a new topic provide an opportunity for what is known as "feeling" the structure over itself. Students learn the basic principles of this construction very quickly. In fact, grammar and vocabulary are not the main object in mastering new material, but they are used as auxiliary material. Thus, assimilation is carried out in automatic mode.

Sixth, the teaching system is suitable for those who wish to read modern texts in their original form, including fiction books, as well as newspapers and magazines published in English. In fact, many connoisseurs of literary works believe that the author's style, the character of each character, and the general mood are much better read in the original text. If you want to enjoy the works of your favorite author as fully as possible, it is recommended to visit the clearly illustrated courses. Since the system, as mentioned above, undertakes to use only real texts, the ability to read the original will quickly appear. In addition, reading books and magazines will be very easy, because the vocabulary and different expressions will not be foreign. It is easy to get various words from educational texts that can be used not only in the process of communication, but also when reading literature. And, of course, the system will definitely help you learn to write competently and even beautifully.

Seventh, the communicative method can help those who want to improve their pronunciation. Frequent use of speech allows you to learn the correct pronunciation of various foreign words in a short time. In this way, the most correct pronunciation was developed. Classes involve lots of conversation and students begin to use different sounds more accurately in speech until the sound is just right. Some activities include pronunciation exercises for certain sounds.

Eighth, the system is perfect for those who want to master the material without getting bored in any class. You will not be bored in the courses taught using this technology. Modern textbooks offer a variety of topics for discussion - always different for each lesson. And each topic will definitely be useful later in life when visiting different countries or interacting with foreigners.

In addition, each lesson contains interesting tools to make the process interesting. Today, without knowing foreign languages, it is difficult to find a promising high-paying job, knowing languages is your achievement, an opportunity for a decent life. The communicative method helps a lot in this. You can also use Ilya Frank's reading method, which will help you improve your vocabulary significantly.

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